

QUALITY OF WORK LIFE: PERCEPTION OF SCHOOLS TEACHERS - CASES TUDY: SCHOOL TEACHERS IN KERMANSHAH, IRAN

Sobhani Aliasgar

Executive Master of Business Administration,
Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj Branch, Iran

Abstract:

The research study was taken to investigate the quality of work life of secondary school teachers. The sample of 135 Secondary School Teachers from Kermanshah City was selected to adopting Stratified random sampling technique. Considering the independent variable namely Gender, Length of experience, and type of schools the stratification was made. Teachers' quality of work life was accessed with the help of Teacher's Quality of Work Life Scale constructed by the investigator. Specific objectives formulated were: 1. To assess the level of quality of Work Life of Secondary School teachers. 2. To find whether there is any significant difference in Quality of Work Life of Secondary School Teachers with male and female. 3. To find whether there is any significant difference in quality of Work Life of Secondary School Teachers with high and low experience. 4. To find whether there is any significant difference in Quality of Work Life of Secondary School teachers belonging to Government, Private aided and Private un-aided Schools. The descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. The data, which was obtained from that survey, was analyzing using percentage analysis, t-test and one-way ANOVA. Findings of the study were 1. A majority (73.8%) of the secondary school teachers in Kermanshah was found to possess an average level of quality of work life and (6.9%) were found to possess low level of quality of work life. Only (19.3%) of the teachers possessed high level of quality of work life. 2. There is a significance difference of Quality of Work life of male and female secondary school teachers comparing teachers mean scores it is found that the female teachers have a high quality of work life than their male counterparts. 3. There is no significance difference between above 10 years experience and below 10 years of experienced secondary school teachers in their Quality of Work Life. 4. There is no significant difference is the quality of work life of teachers belonging to government, private aided, and private unaided secondary school teachers.

JEL: J81, H75, I21

Keywords: quality of work, life, secondary school teachers

1. Introduction

Effective schools emphasize and reinforce the value of human resources and other internal morale issues among their members while being sensitive to external demands (Cameron, 1984). For school operation, teachers are one of the most important human resources. The success of any educational system depends largely on quality teachers. The strengths and quality of any educational system depends largely upon their teacher's work. Work is an integral part of everyday life as it is the livelihood or career. On an average, people spend around twelve hours per day in the work place which forms one third of their entire life. Hence, work should yield satisfaction, give peace of mind, fulfillment of having done a task and having spent time fruitfully, constrictively and purposefully. Even if it is a small step towards the life time goal, at the end of the day it should give satisfaction, eagerness to look forward to the next day. This has led to the quest for improvement in quality of work life. Thus, the quest for quality has been the characteristics of the entire history of human civilization. It has been the driving force behind all human endeavors, quality and quality of work is apparently related to the nature of educational organization. The organizational climate of educational institutions should enhance quality of work life of its teachers.

2. Quality of Work Life

In the post-modern era, several factors which have evolved have led to an increase in concern for Quality of Work Life (QWL). Increase in education level and consequently job aspirations of employees, association of workers, significance of human resource management, widespread unrest in work place and knowledge and behavior of workers in the recent years have created a demand for research on the concept of Quality of work life. The concept of Quality of Work Life is based on the assumption that a job is more than just a job. It is the core of a person's life. This value based process is aimed towards meeting the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of organization and improved quality of life at work for employees. It is concerned with increasing employee management cooperatives to solve the problems of improving organizational performance and employee satisfaction.

The term 'Quality of Work Life' (QWL) has different meanings to different people. Some consider it as democracy or codetermination with increased employee participation in the decision making process. For administrators, the term denotes improvement in the psychological aspects of work to improve productivity. Employees interpret QWL as more equitable sharing of profits, job security and healthy and humane working conditions. Others view it as improving social relationships at workplace through autonomous workgroups. Some take a broader view of changing the entire organizational climate by humanizing work, individualizing organizations and changing the structural and managerial systems. It is also referred to as favorableness or unfavorableness of job environment for people working in it and the quality of relationship between employees and the total working environment. Robbins (1989) defined Quality of work life as, *"A process by which an organization responds to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow them to share fully in making the decisions that design their lives at work"*. Goodman defines, *"Quality of work life is an attempt to restructure multiple dimensions of the organization and to institute a mechanism which introduces and sustains changes over time"*. Richard E. Walton explains quality of work life in terms of eight broad conditions of employee that constitute desirable quality of work life. He proposed the following criteria for measuring quality of work life: Adequate and fair salary: The committee on fair salaries defined fair pay as, *"the pay which is above the minimum salary below the living wage"*. Safe and healthy working conditions: Most of the educational organizations provide safe and healthy working conditions due to humanitarian requirements and legal requirements. Opportunity to use and develop human capacities: The extents that the teacher can exercise more control over his her work, and the degree to which the teaching job embraces an entire meaningful task, but not a part of it. Further quality of work life provides for opportunities like autonomy in work and participation in planning in order to use human capabilities. Opportunity for career growth: Future opportunity for continued growth and security by expanding one's capabilities, knowledge and qualifications contributes to Quality of work life. Opportunities for promotions are limited in case of teachers either due to educational barriers or due to limited openings at the higher level. Social integration in the work force: Social integration in the work force can be established by creating freedom from prejudice, supporting primary work groups to have a sense of community and inter personal openness, egalitarianism and upward mobility of teachers.

Constitutionalism in the work organization: Quality of work life provides constitutional protection to the teachers only to the level of desirability as it hampers work. It happens because the educational management's action is challenged in every action and bureaucratic procedures that need to be followed at that level and is

provided to employees on such matters as privacy, freedom to speak, and equity. Work and quality of life: Quality of work life provides for the balanced relationship among work, non-work and family aspects of life. In other words, family life and social life should not be strained by working hours including overtime work, work during inconvenient hours travel, transfers, and vacations. Social relevance of work: Quality of work life is concerned about the establishment of social relevance to work in a socially beneficial manner. The self-esteem would be high if the teacher's work is useful to the society.

3. Need and Importance of the Study

The study is mainly intends to measure the status of quality of work life of secondary school teachers. In the changing environment of modern technological advancement, the traditional concept of the teaching profession is subjected to rapid changes. A person who enjoys the work and derives satisfaction alone can perform in the best perfect manner. The fulfillment of personal needs and goals leads to satisfaction wellbeing and happiness. But how far and how long could an individual be satisfied in the profession, if it is full of work related stress and strain. The phrase "Quality of Work Life" (QWL) has come in use recently to evoke a broad range of working conditions and the related aspirations and expectations of the teachers. Quality of education entails the design of work systems that enhance the working life experiences of teachers, thereby improving commitment and motivation for achieving their goals. In this regard quality of work life is very important to teacher. Hence, there is a need to study the Quality of work life of secondary school teachers. The review of related literature shows that in the field of education there have been no attempts to study the Quality of Work Life of secondary school teachers. Hence, this research study is a modest venture in this direction.

4. Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the level of quality of Work Life of Secondary School teachers.
2. To find whether there is any significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life.
3. To find whether there is any significant difference between high and low experienced teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life.

4. To find whether there is any significant difference between Secondary School teachers belonging to Government, Private aided and Private un-aided schools with respect to their Quality of Work Life.

5. Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life.
2. There is no significant difference between high and low experienced teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life.
3. There is no significant difference between secondary school teachers belonging to government, private aided and private unaided schools with respect to their Quality of Work Life.

6. Methodology

The present study was taken up to investigate the Quality of Work Life of secondary school teachers and to find whether there is any difference in these variables with respect to type of schools, gender and length of experience. Descriptive survey method of study was followed.

6.1 Variables of the study

- **Main Variable:** Quality of Work Life.
- **Background variables:** Gender, Length of Experience, and type of School.
- **Sample of the study:** The study was conducted on a sample of 135 teachers of Kermanshah. The selection of secondary school teachers was done on the basis of random sampling method.

6.2 Tools Used For Data Collection

The following tools used to collect the data: "Teacher's Quality of Work Life Scale" constructed by the investigator was used. The scale contains 75 statements which represent the universe of content. Hence, it has content validity. It has also construct validity as items were selected having the 't' values equal to or more than 1.75. (Allen L. Edwards, 1975). The scale was given to experts in the field of education and Psychology they agreed that the items in the scale were relevant to the objectives of the study. Hence, it has face validity also. The present study employed Cronbach's Alpha method

to determine the reliability. The reliability of the Cronbach's Alpha test is found to be 0.927.

6.3 Procedure for Data Collection

Data for the study was collected by administering the Teacher's Quality of Work Life Scale to the selected sample by the investigator. The obtained data with respect to different back ground variables were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis employing appropriate statistical techniques.

6.4 Statistical Techniques Used For Analysis of Data

The obtained data was analyzed using Percentage 't' test, and one way ANOVA.

7. Analysis of Data and Interpretation of Results

The analysis of data interpretation and discussion of the results are presented below:

A. Objective 1: to assess the level of Quality of Work Life of Secondary School Teachers

Table 1: Table showing the percentage of secondary school teachers with respect to different levels of Quality of Work Life

Levels of quality of work life	Criteria	Score limit	t Percentage of secondary school teachers	
			Frequency	Percentage
High	Above $M+\sigma$	287-335	22	19.3
Average	Between $M-\sigma$ and $M+\sigma$	252-298	87	73.8
Low	Below $M-\sigma$	62-231	26	6.9
Total			100	100

Analysis related to objective 1 is presented in Table 1. Table 1 reveals that majority of teachers that is 73.8 of secondary school teachers possess average level of quality of work life. It also seen that 19.3 and 6.9 of the secondary school teachers possess high and low level of quality of work life.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life. 't'test was calculated to test the hypothesis 1. The results are presented in Table 2

Table 2: Summary table of 't' test of Quality of Work Life of male and female secondary school teacher

	Gender	N	Mean	S. D	't' value	df	Level of significance
Quality of Work Life	Male	89	298.65	25.87	3.61	95	S at 0.05
	Female	46	311.24	20.17			

Table 2 shows that the obtained 't' value of 3.61 is greater than the tabled 't' value of 1.95 at 0.05 level of significance for degrees of 95. Therefore, the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significance difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life. Comparing the mean value it is found that female teachers have a better quality of Work Life comparing to the male counterparts.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between high and low experienced teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life. 't' test was calculated to test the hypothesis 2. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary table of 't' test of Quality of Work Life of male and female secondary school teachers

Quality Of Work Life	Gender	N	Mean	S. D	't' value	df	Level of significance
Quality Of Work Life	Above 10 years of experience	68	308.65	17.25	0.845	95	NS
	Below 10 years of experience	37	298.64	19.87			

Table 3 reveals that the obtained 't' value of 0.845 is less than the tabled 't' value of 1.95 at 0.05 level of significance for degrees of 95. Therefore the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between above 10 years' experience and below 10 years experience of secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significance difference between above 10 years experience and below 10 years experience of secondary school teachers with respect to their Quality of Work Life.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between secondary school teachers belonging to government, private aided and private unaided schools with respect to their Quality of Work Life. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to test the hypothesis 3. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary table of one way ANOVA of quality of work life of secondary school teachers belonging to government, aided and unaided schools

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	1125.935	5	598.32	1.120	NS
Within groups	42128.214	95	425.68		
Total	43254.149	100			

Table 4 shows that the obtained f value of 1.120 is less than the tabled 'F' value of 3.1 at 0.05 level of significance for degrees of freedom 5 and 95. Therefore, the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between secondary school teachers belonging to government, private aided and private unaided schools with respect to their Quality of Work Life is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in secondary school teachers belonging to government, aided and unaided schools with respect to quality of work life.

8. Findings of the Study

1. A majority (73.8%) of the secondary school teachers in Kermanshah was found to possess an average level of quality of work life and (6.9%) were found to possess low level of quality of work life. Only (19.3%) of the teachers possessed high level of quality of work life.
2. There is a significance difference of Quality of Work life of male and female secondary school teachers comparing teachers mean scores it is found that the female teachers have a high quality of work life than their male counterparts.
3. There is no significance difference between above 10 years experience and below 10 years of experienced secondary school teachers in their Quality of Work Life.
4. There is no significant difference is the quality of work life of teachers belonging to government, private aided, and private unaided secondary school teachers.

9. Educational Implications

1. High quality of work life is to be ensured by educational department to attract and retain teachers; program should be designed to improve quality of work life of teachers. High quality of work life indicate a deep and stable values among its teachers and therefore indicates job security, equitable pay and rewards, justice in the work place, meaningful and interesting work, control over self, work and work place, work authority, and contribute to individual and school

effectiveness. Hence, it has to be ensured that the school environment and school practices cater to the improvement of these components of Quality of Work Life.

2. A significant difference was found between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to Quality of Work Life. It is found that the female teachers have a better Quality of Work Life than their male counter parts. Development of teachers involves training, skill developments, recognition, and promotion. Work assignments should be made challenging enough to expand skills, abilities, and knowledge they should create a positive effects on Quality of Work Life.
3. Opportunity for creativity, job enrichment and reward management are a five strategy used by Human Resource Managers to increase the level of Quality of Work Life in corporate sector, these strategies could also be adapted in educational organizations, so that Quality of work life of teachers could be improved. This would also help in retaining effective and efficient teachers in the profession.

10. Conclusion

The researcher suggest the teachers to motivate full time an teacher counselor to receive his/her service who will help the teachers to solve their personal problems related to work life. If the teachers improve the quality of work life and work culture of the school and individually it should be beneficial for the effective functioning of the educational organization. Because teachers learn, school values and believes through socialization. In this regard, head master of the school should be trained motivated to develop their colleagues in well and effective manner.

References

1. Aswathappa K., "Human Resource and Personnel Management", Second edition (2002), Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing Company, New Delhi.
2. Best. J. W. and Kahn J.V. (1986), "Research in Education", (5th edition) Englewood cliffs, N. J. Prentice-Hall.
3. Buchanan, D. A., & Boddy, D. (1982), "Advanced technology and the quality of Work Life" Journal of Occupational Psychology, Vol.55.
4. Chander, Subash and Singh, Parampal (1983), "Quality of work life in a University: An Empirical Investigation", Management and Labour Studies, Vol.18, No.2, pp. 97- 101.

5. David Efraty and M. Joseph Sirgy (1998), The effects of quality of working life (QWL) on employee behavioral responses Quality of work life. Social Indicators Research, Volume 22, Number 1, 31-47, DOI: 10.1007/BF00286389.
6. Guna Seelan Rethinam and Maimunah Ismail (2008), Constructs of Quality of Work Life: A Perspective of Information and Technology Professionals. European Journal of Social Sciences – Volume 7, Number 1
7. Nadler, D. A., Lawler, E. E., III (1983)'Quality of work life: Perceptions and direction' Organizational Dynamics112030
8. Sirgy, M. J., Efraty, D., Siegel, P., Dong-Jin, L. (2001), A new measure of quality of work life (QWL) based on need satisfaction and spillover theories Social Indicators Research 55241302
9. Taylor, J. C. (1978)'An empirical examination of the dimensions of quality of working life' Omega6153160
10. Walton, R. (1975) Criteria for quality of work life' Davis, L. E. Cherns, R.L. eds. The Quality of Working Life: Problems, Prospects, and the State of the Art Free Press New York 1254 Vol. 1.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain copyright to their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Economic and Financial Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).